

Studies in Spiro-heterocycles. Part-XIV. Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activities of certain Fluorine-containing Spiro[3*H*-indole-3,5'-isoxazolin]-2(1*H*)-ones

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Several new fluorine-containing spiro[3*H*-indole-3,5'-isoxazolin]-2(1*H*)-ones have been synthesised by the reaction of 3-arylmethyleneindol-2-ones with hydroxylamine hydrochloride. The former reactants were obtained by the reaction of indole-2,3-dione with methyl ketones followed by dehydration. Representative compounds gave promising results when screened for antibacterial and antifungal activity.

VARIOUS indole derivatives show antidepressive¹, anti-inflammatory² and hallucinogenic³ activities. Serotonin, an indole derivative, is an important brain amine and plays a significant role as modulator of CNS neurochromonal activity⁴. Further, if the indole ring is joined to other heterocyclic systems through a spiro-carbon atom, the resulting compounds show an increased spectrum of biological activities. Spiro-indole-isoxazolines are useful as CNS drugs⁵ and anti-inflammatory agents⁶ and also act as aldose reductase inhibitors⁷. The role of fluorine in heterocyclic compounds is noteworthy in view of profound changes in biological activities on incorporation of fluorine⁸.

Keeping the above observations in view, various fluorine-containing spiro-isoxazolines have been

synthesised and screened for antibacterial and antifungal activities. Fluorine-containing spiro[3*H*-indole-3,5'-isoxazolin]-2(1*H*)-ones (5) were obtained by the condensation of hydroxylamine hydrochloride with equimolar amount of fluorine-containing 3-arylmethylene-indol-2-ones (4) in alkaline medium. The latter compounds were prepared by dehydration of fluorine-containing 3-hydroxy-3-phenacyl-indol-2-ones (3) which, in turn, were obtained by the reaction of indole-2,3-dione (1) and the acetophenones (2) as shown in Scheme 1.

In compounds 5, ir bands have been observed in the region 1730-1700 (C=O) and 1660-1600 cm⁻¹ (C=N). In ¹H nmr spectrum (DMSO-d₆), signals have been observed at δ 2.5-2.3 (s, CH₃) and 7.6-6.6 ppm (m, ArH). The ¹⁹F nmr spectrum

X = 5-F, 6-F, 4-OF;
R = H, COOH,
R' = H, 3-Cl, 3-CH₃, 2-CH₃.

Scheme 1

(DMSO- d_6) of **5a** shows two signals at δ 119.2 and 120.8 ppm due to fluorine attached at the two different phenyl rings. In ^{13}C nmr spectrum (DMSO- d_6) of **5a** sharp signals have been observed at δ 164 (C=O), 162 (C=N), 152, 146, 143, 138, 124, 118, 117.9, 117.6, 116, 115, 114 and 112 (aromatic carbons), 111.6 (spiro-C) and 111.3 ppm (CH_2); (M^+) at m/z 300.

Experimental

M ps. were determined in open glass capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer, 1H nmr spectra were on a Jeol FX 90Q spectrometer at 89.55 MHz using TMS as internal reference and DMSO- d_6 as solvent, and ^{13}C nmr and ^{19}F nmr spectra on Jeol FX 90Q spectrometer and taken in DMSO- d_6 at 22.49 and 84.25 MHz, respectively using C_6F_6 (at δ -162.9 ppm) as external reference in the latter case. The mass spectra were recorded on a Kratos MS-30 and MS-50 spectrometer operating at an ionisation potential of 70 eV.

Fluorine-containing indole-2,3-diones (1), fluorine-containing 3-hydroxy-3-phenacyl-indol-2-ones (3) and fluorine-containing-3-aroilmethylene-indole-2-ones (4): The compounds were synthesised by literature method⁹.

Fluorine-containing spiro[3H-indole-3,5'-isoxazolin]-2(1H)-ones (5a-j): A mixture of 3-aroilmethylene-indol-2-one (0.02 mol), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.02 mol), potassium hydroxide (2 g), aqueous ethanol (100 ml) was refluxed¹⁰ for 3 h. The resulting precipitate on concentration and cooling was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

Antimicrobial activities: Compounds **5b-j** of the series were evaluated for antimicrobial activities. The filter paper disc method¹¹ was used in screening the ethanolic solution of compounds for antibacterial activity. Standard size blank Whatmann filter paper disc (6.5 mm) sterilised by dry heat at 140° for 1 h were saturated with the solution (1% in absolute ethanol) and the known quantity of standard reference antibiotic separately. These were air-dried at room temperature to remove any residual solvent which might interfere with the determination. The discs were then placed on the surface of a sterilised agar nutrient medium that had been inoculated with the test organism (using a sterile swab) and air-dried to remove the surface moisture. Thickness of the agar medium was kept equal in all petri plates, and standard disc (streptomycin, 10 μg ml⁻¹) was used in each plate as a control. Before incubation, petri dishes were placed for 1 h in a cold room (5°) to allow diffusion of the compounds from the disc into the agar plate. These were incubated at 37° for 20-24 h (except for test fungi which required 48 h) after which the zone of inhibition or depressed growth was measured. All experiments were in five replicates and the values computed. The effect was studied on both types of bacteria, viz. gram-positive *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus faecalis* and gram-negative *Escherichia coli* and *Enterobacter cloacae*.

For antifungal screening, spore suspension (5 ml) of each test organisms (72 h culture) was added to sterilised potato dextrose agar (PDA) medium (100 ml) at 35-40° by thorough shaking. The petri dishes were seeded with the mixture and the paper discs of the ethanolic solution of compound (1% in absolute alcohol) and the reference antibiotic (mycostatin, 100 units/ml; Sarabhai Chemicals) as also the controls were placed in the same manner

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF SPIRO[3H-INDOLE-3,5'-ISOXAZOLIN]-2(1H)-ONES (5)

Compd. no.	X	R	R ¹	Yield %	M p. °C	Mol. formula	N % : Found/ (Calcd.)
5a	5-F	H	H	81	289(d)	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ F ₂ N ₂ O ₂	9.80 (9.33)
5b	5-F	H	3-Cl	86	255	C ₁₆ H ₉ F ₂ ClN ₂ O ₂	8.12 (8.07)
5c	5-F	H	3-CH ₃	83	255(d)	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ F ₂ N ₂ O ₂	8.98 (8.91)
5d	5-F	H	2-CH ₃	82	245	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ F ₂ N ₂ O ₂	8.89 (8.91)
5e	5-F	COOH ₃	3-Cl	80	275	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ F ₂ N ₂ O ₂	7.41 (7.43)
5f	6-F	H	H	84	185	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ F ₂ N ₂ O ₂	9.40 (9.33)
5g	6-F	H	3-Cl	87	260	C ₁₆ H ₉ F ₂ ClN ₂ O ₂	8.12 (8.07)
5h	6-F	H	3-CH ₃	81	235	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ F ₂ N ₂ O ₂	8.95 (8.91)
5i	6-F	H	2-CH ₃	85	230	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ F ₂ N ₂ O ₂	8.90 (8.91)
5j	4-CF ₃	H	H	72	242	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ F ₃ N ₂ O ₂	7.99 (8.00)

TABLE 2—ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITIES OF SPIRO[3H-INDOLE-3,5'-ISOXAZOLIN'-2(1H) ONES (5)

Organism	Inhibition zone in mm/(Activity index)*							
	5b	5c	5d	5f	5g	5h	5i	5j
<i>E. coli</i>	—	—	10.0 (4.1)	—	—	13.0 (5.4)	—	—
<i>E. cloacae</i>	—	—	—	—	9.0 (4.5)	—	10.0 (5.0)	—
<i>S. aureus</i>	21.0 (17.5)	14.0 (11.6)	15.0 (12.5)	12.0 (10.0)	—	9.0 (7.5)	15.0 (12.5)	—
<i>S. faecalis</i>	—	25.0 (8.3)	20.0 (6.6)	10.0 (3.3)	15.0 (5.0)	10.0 (3.3)	22.0 (7.3)	25.0 (8.3)
<i>A. flavus</i>	7.0 (3.8)	8.0 (4.4)	14.0 (7.7)	8.0 (4.4)	9.0 (5.0)	20.0 (11.1)	8.0 (4.4)	10.0 (5.5)
<i>C. lunata</i>	12.0 (6.0)	10.0 (5.0)	14.0 (17.7)	12.0 (6.6)	12.0 (6.0)	—	—	9.0 (4.5)
<i>D. tetramera</i>	—	—	8.0 (4.0)	20.0 (10.0)	12.0 (6.0)	12.0 (6.0)	—	—
<i>C. albicans</i>	16.0 (12.3)	—	10.0 (7.6)	15.0 (11.5)	12.0 (9.2)	9.0 (6.9)	7.0 (5.3)	—

(—) = Not measurable activity. *Activity index = $\frac{\text{Inhibition area of the sample}}{\text{Inhibition area of the standard}}$

as in the antibacterial activity determination. These petri dishes were incubated at 30° for 48 h. The zone of inhibition was considered as an indicator for the antifungal activity. The fungi against which the activity were tested are *Aspergillus flavus*, *Curvularis lunata*, *Drechslera tetramera* and *Candida albicans*.

The results of antibacterial and antifungal activities are expressed in Table 2. Most of the compounds are active against gram-(+) bacteria but show better activity against gram(-). Except 5b, all compounds are active against *S. faecalis*. Compounds 5c and 5j show maximum activity (zone of inhibition, 25.0 mm). Compound 5b, however, shows highest activity against *S. aureus* (zone of inhibition, 21.0 mm). All compounds are active against the fungus *A. flavus*, while 5d, 5f and 5g are active against all fungi. Compound 5f shows maximum activity against *D. tetramera* (zone of inhibition, 20.0 mm). The activity of the compounds may be attributed to the presence of fluorine in the nucleus.

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